

**University
of Basel**

Institute for
Educational Sciences

VALISE

Values in School Education
Wertebildung in der Schule

Technical Report

The Formation of Children's Values in School: A Study on Value Development Among Primary School Children in Switzerland and the United Kingdom

September 2020 – July 2022

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1. Introduction

1.1 Initial situation and project description

This research project will illuminate how primary schools shape children's personal value development, by employing a longitudinal design in Switzerland along with a comparative cross-sectional study in the UK. The project builds on our experience and successful joint projects in classroom research and human value development. The project will set the foundations for theory building on formation of values in the school context. This knowledge is essential for providing evidence-based guidance for values education in schools.

The formation of children's values in primary school is at the core of school curricula and educational frameworks in Europe, and more specifically in Switzerland (Lehrplan 21; D-EDK, 2014) and the UK (National Curriculum; Department of Education, 2014). Values express broad goals (kindness, curiosity) that are important to a person in life, and they are linked to behaviour (Bardi & Schwartz, 2003; Maio, 2010). Primary schools are expected to develop children's understanding of their own and others' values, children's ability to express their own values and pursue behaviours that help achieving them. In most recent years there has been a steep increase of publications, including the first special section on value development from childhood to early adulthood (Döring, Daniel, & Knafo-Noam, 2016) and research which highlights the impact of the family context (Makarova, Herzog, Weber, & Frommelt, 2018) and value-based educational goals on children's value development (Döring, Makarova, Herzog, & Bardi, 2017). However, the field is still surprisingly under-researched, and there is a lack of evidence of how children's values develop and how they are formed in primary school. The proposed four-year collaborative project (Switzerland and UK) will help fill this research gap by proposing the socio-ecological model of value formation in school and investigating the formation of children's values longitudinally. The project is going to answer the question:

How do key variables of the micro-, meso-, and macro-school-system affect children's values over time? By focussing on two research objectives:

Objective 1: *To research children's value priorities and behaviours in the school context in Switzerland and the UK.*

We will investigate children's values in the microsystem (proximal processes within classrooms), the mesosystem (investigating the effect of school climate), and the macrosystem (investigating the effect of educational policies and national curricula in each country). To meet this objective a cross-sectional study in grade 1 in Switzerland (n=1000 children, 40 school classes) and the UK (n=500, 20 school classes) will be conducted, with a focus on proximal processes within the classroom, collecting data from pupils and their class teacher. The cross-national comparison will generate knowledge on effects of national value-related curricula on children's value priorities and behaviours generating empirical evidence on implementation of value education in both countries, Switzerland and the UK.

Objective 2: *To investigate developmental trajectories of children's value priorities in primary school.* We will additionally investigate trajectories over time, hence investigating effects in the chronosystem. A two-year longitudinal study with four points of measurements (grades 1 to 2) will be launched in Switzerland, which will identify trajectories of value development in school –being the first such study. Identifying proximal key factors that affect children's formation of values in classrooms and studying their impact will significantly advance theory building on value development. The project team brings together unique strengths in relevant research areas (assessment of children's values, value change, value development in childhood, the relationship between values and behaviour, social inclusion in classrooms, pupil-teacher relationship), world-leading research and well-established networks with schools, teacher training institutions, educational authorities, and scientists for dissemination of findings. The findings from this project will be published in leading international journals with a focus on open science. The findings will be publicised worldwide through networks and values research centres, and disseminated widely to teachers, school principals, politicians, and the wider public.

1.2 Objectives of the research report

This research report serves as the technical documentation of the first research phase of the research project. It aims to present the recruitment and methodological approach of the quantitative data collection (see chapter 2), the procedure for the survey (see chapter 3), the

main survey (see chapter 4), the realised samples from T1 to T4 (see chapter 5), the preparation of data (see chapter 6), the adjustments after data collections (see chapter 7), references (see chapter 8) and the appendix (chapter 9).

2. Recruitment and methodological approach

The research design of the project includes a longitudinal study in Switzerland and a cross-sectional comparison with the United Kingdom. For this reason, the sample recruitment will take place in both countries mentioned. Only the Swiss approach is described in detail below.

2.1 Anticipated sample

For the anticipated sample of the first project phase in Switzerland (period September 2020 - May 2021), it was planned to recruit pupils of the 1st grade of primary school class and their class teachers. There were two inclusion criteria: On the one hand, the teachers should teach the pupils continuously from the beginning of grade 1 to the end of grade 2. Secondly, the teachers have to teach according to the Lehrplan 21 (Curriculum 21), which was introduced in the first cantons of Switzerland in 2016. The classes were recruited in the seven cantons of Aargau, Bern, Basel-Landschaft, Basel-Stadt, Lucerne, Solothurn and St. Gallen. All of these cantons had already introduced Curriculum 21 in their schools at the time of the survey.

The aim was to recruit a total of approx. 50-60 teachers and their classes (N=1'500 pupils) from the cantons indicated.

2.2 Sample recruitment

In a first step, the cantonal authorities were contacted in order to obtain the consent of the heads of the primary school offices to recruit in the primary schools of the respective cantons. After approval, a list of all eligible schools in the seven cantons was drawn up (criteria: 1st grade, introduction of Curriculum 21).

The next step was (a) to contact the school headmasters by means of a project flyer and a letter containing all the information about the study (b) to contact the teachers of the participating classes who had been notified to us by the school headmasters. In total, 649 schools in the

seven cantons could be approached based on permission and fulfilment of the specified criteria. Divided among the cantons, the following picture emerges (see Tab. 1).

Table 1 Willingness of schools to participate (sorted by canton) (as of 06.01.21)

Canton	AG	BE	BL	BS	LU	SG	SO	in total
Requests	218	117	70	30	104	43	67	649
Declines	184	108	47	23	91	40	58	551
Confirmations	34	9	22	7	13	3	9	97

2.3 Contacting the cantons

Canton Aargau

Once the head of the section "Organisation and Development of the Elementary School" of the Department of Education and Sports of the Canton of Aargau (BKS) had agreed, the project team collected the contact details of all Aargau schools on the website www.schulen-aargau.ch. The necessary data (address and the selection of the schools) were supplemented by the information on the websites of the respective schools.

Canton Bern

Permission to inquire with the primary schools of the Canton of Bern was given by the head of the Office for Kindergarten, Elementary School and Counselling (AKVB). Once permission had been granted, the size of the schools (number of potential classes) and the geographical location of the schools in relation to Basel were taken into account in addition to the existing criteria when selecting the schools for reasons of research economy.

Canton Basel-Landschaft

The deputy head of the Basel-Landschaft primary schools (AVS) also gave the project management permission to recruit primary schools in Basel-Landschaft for the research project. For this purpose, the team used the file "Primarstufe" (primary level), which can be

found on the cantonal website of Basel-Landschaft and lists all schools in the canton. For further information on the individual primary schools the individual school websites were used.

(Basel-Landschaft primary school: <https://www.baselland.ch/politik-und-behorden/direktionen/bildungs-kultur-und-sportdirektion/bildung/primarstufe>)

Canton Basel-Stadt

The Basel-Stadt primary school's administration (EduBS) allowed those responsible for the project to write directly to the school administrations of the primary schools in the canton of Basel-Stadt for the study. For this purpose, the project team used the file "Overview of the school locations of Basel-Stadt", which is available on the website of the Department of Education of the Canton of Basel-Stadt. Further data on the primary schools were extracted from their respective websites. (Basel-Stadt primary school: <https://www.volksschulen.bs.ch/schulen/standorte.html>)

Canton Lucerne

The Office of Primary Education in Lucerne (DVS) granted permission to contact the school headmasters of the primary level in the Canton of Lucerne for the study. In order to contact all schools in the canton, the project team used the file "Schulliste" (school list) listed on the website of the Volksschulbildung Luzern. Further data on the primary schools were extracted from their own websites. (Adult Education Lucerne: https://volksschulbildung.lu.ch/syst_schulen/ss_schulliste)

Canton Solothurn

The project team also received permission from the Volksschulamt Solothurn (VSA) to enquire about the individual primary schools in the canton. For this purpose, a list of all schools and school administrations in the canton was found on the website of the Volksschulamt via "Schulbetrieb und Unterricht". From this list, the project team filtered out all primary schools that met the criteria described above. For more detailed information on the individual schools, the websites of the individual schools were used. (Volksschule Solothurn: <https://so.ch/verwaltung/department-fuer-bildung-und-kultur/volksschulamt/schulbetrieb-und-unterricht/>)

Canton St. Gallen

For the Canton of St. Gallen, the management of the Office for Adult Education (AVS) granted permission to contact the schools regarding participation in the study. As in the case of the Canton of Bern, geographical aspects and the size of the school were also taken into account when recruiting the schools in the Canton of St. Gallen.

2.4 Contacting the schools

All selected school headmasters (N = 649) received an email request with information about the project and the project flyer. In the enquiry email, the head teachers were informed about the topic of the project and the procedure. In addition, it was pointed out that the current situation (due to the Corona pandemic) and the resulting need to comply with the cantonal protection concepts would be taken into account in the survey in spring 2021. The enquiry email also informed that the project team would contact the head teachers by telephone within the next two weeks. All project staff studied a telephone guide in order to be able to respond to the telephone enquiries in a trained and competent manner. In total class teachers from 97 schools in the seven cantons were recruited.

Figure 1 Graphical representation of the number of possible and recruited schools by canton

2.5 Contacting the class teachers

On the one hand, interested teachers were informed of the project team by their school management via email or telephone. On the other hand, interested teachers contacted the project team themselves by email.

Table 2 Overview of teacher's willingness to participate

Class teachers	AG	BE	BL	BS	LU	SG	SO	in total
Confirmed class teachers	38	10	30	7	13	3	13	114
Class teachers who did not meet the selection criteria	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	4
Selected for longitudinal study	27	10	14	6	8	0	3	68

Selected for cross-sectional study	11	0	16	1	5	3	10	46
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Note: Some of the 97 participating classes have more than two teachers. We let the teachers decide whether both or only the teacher with the larger workload would fill out the questionnaire. From the 114 confirmed teachers finally 108 completed the survey at T1.

After interested teachers contacted the project team, they received an email requesting information such as contact details (school postal address, teacher's telephone number), the number of children in the class, confirmation that the teacher teaches according to Curriculum 21 and that the teacher will teach the class until the end of Year 2. When this information was given to the project team, the teacher was sent an information letter, a project flyer, an appointment form for the survey in March/April 2021, the specified number of parent information items including a project flyer for the parents and a pre-paid return envelope for the teacher's appointment form.

3. Procedure for the survey

3.1 Piloting

In preparation for the main survey, a piloting phase took place in January/February 2021. A total of 8 classes (n~150 pupils) from the cantons of Lucerne, Basel-Stadt, Basel-Land and Bern took part. For this purpose, mixed-grade classes (1st & 2nd grade together) were also recruited in order to test the measurement instruments and questionnaires for the different grades. In this pilot, the children of one half of the classes were interviewed analogue (paper questionnaire and sticker version of the "Picture-Based Value Survey for Children", PBVS-C), the other half digitally with tablets using the questionnaire created on Unipark.

In addition to the children's survey, the teachers (n=10) were also surveyed by means of an online questionnaire. The knowledge gained from the pilot data and the feedback from the respondents made it possible to optimise the questionnaire. For the latter, a feedback form was used.

Overall, the piloting left a positive impression. Some suggestions for optimising conducting of the questionnaire with the children were made (e.g., design issues like bigger and nicer smileys, landscape format for children's questionnaire, slight adjustments to the instructions).

4. Main survey

4.1 Standardised procedure

In February 2021, a training session for all persons (doctoral students, research assistants, research trainees, honorary staff) responsible to conduct the survey took place. The aim of the training was to standardise the survey situation, to discuss the exact procedure step by step and to clarify possible questions and difficulties. With the help of video recordings of the piloting, the survey situation could be presented authentically and a basis for standardised surveys was thus given. It was decided that two people would form a survey team (one lead, one support). The person in the lead function was responsible for reading out the step-by-step instructions (see appendix) and for conducting the entire survey. Depending on the size of the class and how many children were not allowed to participate in the study (e.g., because they were already in the second grade or because their parents did not agree to participate in the project), the second person supported the implementation or took care of the children who did not participate in the project in a separate room. For these children, a sheet with different activities (mandala to colour etc.) was prepared. After the interview, the interview team filled out a standardised protocol (see observation sheet).

4.2 Preparation

A couple days before the survey took place, the interview leaders were instructed to contact the teachers by telephone in order to briefly describe the interview situation again, to clarify possible questions and to be prepared for the current situation in the class (Covid-19 situation, size of the class, other special features). They were also reminded that the children's consent forms would be collected on the day of the survey.

4.3 Conducting the surveys

Usually, the survey was conducted with two people (one lead, one support). If there were many children who were not allowed to participate (reasons: different school year, no parental consent), a second room was organised, where the children were supervised either by the teacher herself/himself or by a person from the survey team. If there were only a few children, who were not allowed to participate, they were kept busy in the classroom with an assignment from the teacher or an employment dossier from the survey team during this time. During the survey, the teacher filled out the online questionnaire in another room.

After a short round of introductions and explanations, all children first had to give their consent to take part in the survey. Children who did not give their consent were given an employment assignment by the survey team. After this introduction (information about the project and consent of the pupils), the instructions were read out step by step and the survey was carried out. Depending on the class situation, one or two 5-minute breaks (either free breaks or guided games) were taken. The second person (support) walked through the class the whole time to clarify possible difficulties or questions. It was very important to the research team that all children answered all questions together. After completing the questionnaire, all children (also those who did not participate in the study) received a sticker as a thank you for their help during the survey (see appendix, 9.7).

4.4 Follow-up

After each survey, the observation form was filled out, and it was reported to the core project team, which children had participated and which had not (sick, no consent, etc.). Furthermore, the observation form contained notes about children, which were conspicuous or had language or cognitive difficulties while completing the questionnaire. In addition, all consent forms were scanned and uploaded into the project database.

After the completion of the first survey, a thank-you card was sent by post to all classes with the signatures of all persons involved in the survey.

At the end of the fourth data collection, the teachers also got a small thank you chocolate for participating in our study.

5. Sample size

At each point in the survey, the relative number of participants differed from the absolute number. The absolute number (data sets) is calculated from the relative number of participants minus those who did not participate, were absent, had not been given a “informed consent form” (ICF) or whose data were removed from the dataset.

5.1 Children’s sample size

The reasons for the unavailability or removal of data for the children were as follows:

- (a) children were absent from the survey (due to illness, appointments or quarantine)
- (b) children did not receive consent from their parents to participate in the study
- (c) children did not want to participate in the survey
- (d) pupils had problems with filling in the questionnaires, according to the survey administration, whereby language difficulties, but also cognitive difficulties were indicated. The questionnaires of these children concerned were checked for plausibility by the project management. Information on the absolute numbers for each survey time point t1-t4 can be seen in the following tables. The relative sample size for each time point varies greatly due to change of residence of the children to another village within the school year.

5.1.1 Realised sample T1

	N
Relative sample size	1461
Absent due to illness, appointments, or quarantine	50
No consent form from parents	232
Did not want to participate	13

Excluded due to language difficulties or cognitive difficulties	29
Absolut sample size T1 (Datasets)	1137

5.1.2 Realised sample T2

	N
Relative sample size	1605
Absent due to illness, appointments, or quarantine	131
No consent form from parents	277
Did not want to participate	7
Excluded due to language difficulties or cognitive difficulties	5
Absolut sample size T2 (Datasets)	1185

5.1.3 Realised sample T3

	N
Relative sample size	1524
Absent due to illness, appointments, or quarantine	118
No consent form from parents	281
Did not want to participate	4
Excluded due to language difficulties or cognitive difficulties	15
Absolut sample size T3 (Datasets)	1106

5.1.4 Realised sample T4

	N
Relative sample size	1451
Absent due to illness, appointments, or quarantine	57
No consent form from parents	281
Did not want to participate	8
Excluded due to language difficulties or cognitive difficulties	3
Absolut sample size T4 (Datasets)	1102

5.2 Teachers' sample size

The reasons for the unavailability or removal of data from the teachers were as follows:

- (a) teachers did not fill out the survey within the allotted time
- (b) teachers did not want to take part in the study anymore

5.2.1 Realised sample T1

	N
Relative sample size	108
(a) did not fill out the survey within the allotted time	0
(b) did not want to take part in the study anymore	0
Absolut sample size T1 (Datasets)	108

5.2.2 Realised sample T2

	N
Relative sample size	108
(a) did not fill out the survey within the allotted time	6
(b) did not want to take part in the study anymore	0
Absolut sample size T2 (Datasets)	102

5.2.3 Realised sample T3

	N
Relative sample size	108
(a) did not fill out the survey within the allotted time	10
(b) did not want to take part in the study anymore	2
Absolut sample size T3 (Datasets)	96

5.2.4 Realised sample T4

	N
Relative sample size	108
(a) did not fill out the survey within the allotted time	13
(b) did not want to take part in the study anymore	12
Absolut sample size T4 (Datasets)	83

6. Preparation of data

The analogue questionnaires were entered by the survey team in Unipark. The digital questionnaires were already stored directly in Unipark. After data cleansing and merging the analogue and digital questionnaires, the student sample was converted into an SPSS file and tested with various statistical methods. The same procedure was done with the teacher's sample.

After all data collections, we created two data files with data from children and data from teachers of all the points of data collection.

7. Archiving and digitalisation

All physical questionnaires of the children were filed and archived in boxes per class during the survey phase. After completion of the last survey time point (T4), a PDF of each child's questionnaire was created, and all scans were anonymised and stored on a server at the University of Basel that was protected from access.

8. Adjustment after data collections

After T1: only analogue questionnaires for the children (no digital version)

After T2-T3: Few questions were added (for further details, see internal research report)

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10. Appendix

(German documents only)

10.1 Informationen zum Projekt

(Webseite: <https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/de/valise/>, 11.05.21)

Wertebildung in der Schule: Eine Studie der Werteentwicklung von Primarschulkindern in der Schweiz und in Grossbritannien

Das Projekt beleuchtet Werteentwicklung von Primarschulkindern in der Schweiz und in Grossbritannien im Zusammenhang mit wertbezogenen Bildungszielen in den Schulcurricula der beiden Länder. Dieses Wissen ist wichtig, um evidenzbasierte Leitlinien für die Wertebildung an Schulen bereitzustellen.

Inhalt und Ziel des Forschungsprojekts

Werte sind ein zentraler Bestandteil der Schulcurricula in der Schweiz und in Grossbritannien. In den beiden Ländern werden die wertbezogenen Kompetenzen von Kindern im Primarschulalter explizit in Lehrplänen abgebildet (z.B. für die Deutschschweiz im Lehrplan21 und für Grossbritannien in den OFSTED- Bildungsstandards). Von den Primarschülerinnen und -schülern wird erwartet, dass sie ein Verständnis für ihre eigenen Werte und die Werte anderer entwickeln, fähig sind, ihre eigenen Werte zu artikulieren und sich dementsprechend zu verhalten. Zugleich ist die Werteentwicklung von Primarschulkindern noch dürftig erforscht. Es fehlt an differenzierten Erkenntnissen dazu, wie die Werte von Kindern im Primarschulalter sich entwickeln und welche Rolle hierbei der schulische Kontext spielt. Das Projekt soll dazu beitragen, diese Forschungslücke zu schließen. Dazu fokussiert

das zwei Länder Kooperationsprojekt (CH und UK) auf zwei Ziele: 1) Entwicklungsverläufe in Werthaltungen, Wertestrukturen, und Werteprioritäten der Kinder durch Längsschnittforschung zu analysieren und 2) jene Schlüsselfaktoren zu identifizieren, die die Werteentwicklung von Kinderwerten im schulischen Kontext beeinflussen.

Wissenschaftlicher und gesellschaftlicher Kontext

Die ländervergleichende und längsschnittliche Studie untersucht Wertebildung im Rahmen eines neuentwickelten sozio-ökologischen Modells der Werteentwicklung im schulischen Kontext. Die Ergebnisse der Studie werden erlauben, Lehrerinnen und Lehrer im Bereich der Wertebildung von Kindern im Primarschulalter weiterzubilden und ihnen Möglichkeiten aufzuzeigen, wie die wertbezogenen Kompetenzen von Kindern im schulischen Kontext gefördert werden können.

Laufzeit: September 2020 - August 2024

10.2 Projektflyer

Wertebildung in der Schule

Was möchten wir untersuchen?

Unser Projekt beleuchtet die Wertentwicklung von Primarschulkindern in der Schweiz und in Grossbritannien im Zusammenhang mit wertbezogenen Bildungszielen der beiden Länder. Dieses Wissen ist wichtig, um Weiterbildungsangebote im Bereich der Wertebildung für Lehrpersonen zu entwickeln.

Wer kann bei unserem Projekt mitmachen?

Wir suchen Lehrpersonen der 1. Klasse aus Kantonen der Deutschschweiz, die nach Lehrplan 21 und ihre Schülerinnen und Schüler von der 1. bis zum Ende der 2. Klasse unterrichten.

Wie läuft das Projekt ab?

Neben einer Befragung der Schülerinnen und Schüler zu ihren Werteeinstellungen, werden wir ebenso die Lehrpersonen mithilfe eines Fragebogens nach ihren eigenen Wertvorstellungen und wertbezogenen Unterrichtszielen befragen.

Die erste Befragung wird im März/April 2021 stattfinden und mit einem Abstand von 4 Monaten insgesamt viermal unter Einhaltung der Schutzkonzepte der Schulen bezüglich der Covid-19 Pandemie wiederholt (siehe Zeitleiste unten).

Was wissen wir nach der Studie?

Erstmals wird im Rahmen unserer Studie der Einfluss von schulbezogenen

Faktoren für die Wertebildung von Primarschulkindern untersucht. Daraus können sehr wichtige Erkenntnisse gewonnen werden, die wegweisend für die Entwicklung wertbezogener Kompetenzen im schulischen Kontext sind.

Was bieten wir an?

Den teilnehmenden Lehrpersonen bieten wir eine auf unseren Ergebnissen basierende Weiterbildung an, die Leitlinien für die Wertebildung von Kindern im Primarschulalter vermittelt und den Lehrpersonen zugleich Möglichkeiten aufzeigt, wie wertbezogene Kompetenzen von Primarschulkindern gefördert werden können.

Was sind Werte?

Was ist mir wichtig? Wie möchte ich leben? Was sind meine Ziele?

Bei all diesen Fragen geht es um **Werte**. Es geht darum, positive Ziele zu formulieren und dem eigenen Leben Richtung und Bedeutung zu geben. Im Leben jedes Menschen gibt es Dinge, die sehr wichtig sind und Dinge, die weniger wichtig sind. Dabei sind Werte nicht nur abstrakte, wünschenswerte Ziele, nach denen Menschen streben. Vielmehr haben Werte eine ganz praktische Bedeutung und beeinflussen soziale Beziehungen, die Entwicklung über die Lebensspanne, Glück und Wohlbefinden und nicht zuletzt unser tägliches Handeln. Darüber hinaus kommt Werten auch eine grosse gesellschaftliche Bedeutung zu (vgl. Döring, 2010).

Kontakt unter:

Prof. Dr. Elena Makarova & VALISE-Projektteam

✉ valise@unibas.ch

☎ +41 61 207 53 33

🌐 <https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/de/valise>

10.3 Anfrageschreiben an die Schulleitung

Sehr geehrter Herr/Frau

Im Rahmen des vom Schweizerischen Nationalfonds unterstützten Forschungsprojekts **VALISE**, welches am Institut für Bildungswissenschaften der Universität Basel durchgeführt wird, untersuchen wir mittels eines Längsschnittvergleichs in der Schweiz und eines Ländervergleichs mit Grossbritannien die **Wertebildung von Primarschulkindern** im Zusammenhang mit wertbezogenen Bildungszielen in den Schulcurricula der beiden Länder. Im Fokus unseres Projekts stehen persönliche Entwicklungsverläufe der Werthaltungen, Wertestrukturen und Werteprioritäten der Kinder sowie die Identifikation jener Schlüsselfaktoren, welche die Werteentwicklung von Kinderwerten im schulischen Kontext beeinflussen (LP21, Schulkultur, Lehrpersonen).

Die Ergebnisse unserer Studie werden erlauben, Lehrpersonen im Bereich der Wertebildung von Kindern im Primarschulalter weiterzubilden und ihnen zugleich Möglichkeiten aufzuzeigen, wie die wertbezogenen Kompetenzen von Kindern im schulischen Kontext gefördert werden können.

Dazu planen wir eine Befragung von Lehrpersonen und Schüler*innen der ersten beiden Klassen der Primarschule in der Deutschschweiz, die im Zeitraum **Frühjahr 2021 bis Sommer 2022** insgesamt **viermal** an einer Befragung im Umfang von **zwei Unterrichtslektionen** teilnehmen. Die Kinder werden durch das Forschungsteam des Instituts für Bildungswissenschaften der Universität Basel befragt. Die Befragung der Lehrperson erfolgt mithilfe eines **Online-Fragebogens**, welcher zeitgleich zur Befragung der Kinder ausgefüllt wird.

Für beide Erhebungen wird strikte **Anonymität** garantiert und die erhobenen Daten werden streng **vertraulich** behandelt. Sie dienen ausschliesslich zum Zweck des Forschungsvorhabens und lassen keinerlei Rückschlüsse auf Einzelpersonen zu. In Anbetracht der aktuellen Covid-19 Situation wird während der Durchführung der Erhebung selbstverständlich **das an Ihrer Schule geltende Schutzkonzept** berücksichtigt.

Wir möchten Sie hiermit höflich anfragen, ob wir mit Ihrer Unterstützung rechnen dürfen und freuen uns sehr darüber, wenn Sie dieses Schreiben sowie den beiliegenden Informationsflyer mit näheren Angaben zum Projekt den **Lehrpersonen Ihrer aktuellen 1. Klassen** weiterleiten. Interessierte Lehrpersonen können sich gerne direkt mit uns in Verbindung setzen, um das weitere Vorgehen zu besprechen. Wir erlauben uns, in den nächsten zwei Wochen nochmals telefonisch Kontakt mit Ihnen aufzunehmen, um den aktuellen Stand zu klären und gegebenenfalls Fragen zum Projekt zu beantworten.

Sollten in der Zwischenzeit Fragen auftauchen, dürfen Sie sich jederzeit auch direkt beim VALISE-Team per E-Mail (unter valise@unibas.ch) oder telefonisch unter +41 61 207 53 33 melden.

Gerne verweisen wir zudem gerne auf unsere Projekt-Homepage (<https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/de/valise>).

Freundliche Grüsse und herzlichen Dank für Ihre wertgeschätzte Unterstützung

Prof. Dr. Elena Makarova & VALISE-Projektteam

10.4 Anfrageschreiben an die Lehrpersonen

Basel, November 2020

Liebe Lehrpersonen

Wir bedanken uns herzlich für die Bereitschaft zur Teilnahme an unserer Studie und teilen Ihnen mit diesem Schreiben gerne die Informationen über den Verlauf des Projekts mit.

Wie bereits im Schreiben an die Schulleitungen erwähnt, werden insgesamt vier Befragungen von Lehrpersonen und Kindern durchgeführt. Die Zeitpunkte der Befragung können Sie dem beiliegenden Flyer entnehmen. Die Befragung der Lehrperson erfolgt mithilfe eines Online-Fragebogens, welcher zeitgleich zur Befragung der Kinder ausgefüllt wird.

Die Befragung erfolgt anonym und die erhobenen Daten werden vertraulich behandelt. Sie dienen ausschliesslich zum Zweck des Forschungsvorhabens und lassen keinerlei Rückschlüsse auf Einzelpersonen zu. In Anbetracht der aktuellen Covid-19-Pandemie wird während der Durchführung unserer Erhebung selbstverständlich das an Ihrer Schule geltende Schutzkonzept gemäss BAG-Empfehlungen und kantonalen Richtlinien berücksichtigt.

Die Kinder werden während insgesamt zwei Unterrichtslektionen durch das Forschungsteam des Instituts für Bildungswissenschaften der Universität Basel befragt. Während dieser Lektionen werden die Kinder Bilder auswählen, wodurch sie sich anhand eines Bildverfahrens zu ihren Werten äussern. Um den Besuch bei Ihnen planen zu können, bitten wir Sie, auf dem beiliegendem Termintalon alle Wochenhalbtage anzukreuzen, an welchen ein Besuch in Ihrer Klasse möglich ist. Wir werden uns im Januar 2021 bei Ihnen melden und mithilfe Ihrer Angaben einen definitiven Termin für die Befragung im Zeitraum März/April 2021 ausmachen.

In der Beilage erhalten Sie die von Ihnen angegebene Anzahl an Informationsschreiben für die Erziehungsberechtigten der Kinder Ihrer Klasse inkl. Flyer und Talon mit der Einverständniserklärung zur Teilnahme an der Studie. Bitte geben Sie diese Schreiben den Kindern mit und teilen Sie uns dann nach der Rückmeldefrist per Mail mit, wie viele Kinder aus Ihrer Klasse am Forschungsprojekt teilnehmen werden. Am Tag der Befragung nehmen wir dann gerne die ausgefüllten Einverständniserklärungen der Eltern entgegen.

Wir bitten Sie, den Termintalon innerhalb 2 Wochen mit dem beiliegenden vorfrankierten Rücksendecouvert (oder per Scan als Mail an valise@unibas.ch) an uns zu retournieren.

Mit Ihrer Zusage leisten Sie einen wichtigen Beitrag zum Gelingen unseres Forschungsprojektes!

Herzlichen Dank dafür!

Freundliche Grüsse

Prof. Dr. Elena Makarova & VALISE-Projektteam

10.5 Rücksendetalon für die Lehrpersonen

Rückmeldetalon

Vorname/Name der Lehrperson: _____

Schule: _____ Klasse: _____

A) Mögliche Vormittage, an denen Sie und Ihre Klasse generell für die Befragung im **März/April** verfügbar sind*:

	Montag	Dienstag	Mittwoch	Donnerstag	Freitag
2 Lektionen vor der Pause (ca. 08.00h – 10.00h)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2 Lektionen nach der Pause (ca. 10.00h – 12.00h)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

*falls auch Nachmittage mögliche wären, bitte hier vermerken:

B) Gibt es an Ihrer Schule ggf. folgende Infrastruktur für die Befragung der Kinder?

	Ja	Nein	Anzahl
- W-LAN	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
- Tablets/Laptop mit integrierter W-LAN Schnittstelle	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	___
- Computerraum inkl. Geräte mit Internetzugang	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	___

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Ansprechpersonen: Ricarda Scholz & Thomas Oeschger

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Webseite: <https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/de/valise>

10.6 Informationsschreiben an die Eltern

**Universität
Basel**

Institut für
Bildungswissenschaften

VALISE

Values in School Education
Wertebildung in der Schule

Basel, November 2020

Liebe Erziehungsberechtigte, liebe Eltern

Die Lehrperson und die Schulklasse, welche ihr Kind besucht, nehmen am Forschungsprojekt VALISE - «Wertebildung in der Schule» teil. Das Projekt wird vom Schweizerischen Nationalfonds (SNF) unterstützt und am Institut für Bildungswissenschaften der Universität Basel durchgeführt. Im Rahmen dieses Projekts möchten wir herausfinden, welche Werte Kindern im Primarschulalter wichtig sind und welchen Einfluss die Schule auf die Werteentwicklung der Kinder hat. Um dies zu untersuchen, möchten wir die Schülerinnen und Schüler ab Frühjahr 2021 insgesamt viermal in einem Abstand von vier Monaten zu ihren Werteinstellungen befragen. Die Befragung, die während zwei Lektionen an der Schule durchgeführt wird, erfolgt, indem die Kinder Bilder auswählen und sich damit auf eine spielerische Art und Weise unter anderem zu ihren Werten, zum Klassenklima oder zum Verhältnis zur Lehrperson äussern.

Die Befragung erfolgt anonym und die erhobenen Daten werden vertraulich behandelt. Sie dienen ausschliesslich zum Zweck des Forschungsvorhabens und lassen keinerlei Rückschlüsse auf Einzelpersonen zu. In Anbetracht der aktuellen Covid-19 Situation wird während der Durchführung unserer Erhebung selbstverständlich das an der Schule geltende Schutzkonzept gemäss BAG-Empfehlungen und kantonalen Richtlinien berücksichtigt.

Durch Ihr Einverständnis tragen Sie zur Erforschung der Werteentwicklung von Kindern bei. Bitte füllen Sie den untenstehenden Talon aus und geben Sie diesen in den nächsten zwei Wochen der Klassenlehrperson Ihres Kindes ab, damit wir wissen, ob ihr Kind an unserem Projekt teilnehmen darf.

Weitere Informationen zum Projekt können Sie auf der Webseite (Link siehe unten) oder dem beigegeführten Flyer entnehmen. Bei Fragen dürfen Sie sich jederzeit direkt beim VALISE-Projektteam (Ansprechpersonen: Ricarda Scholz & Thomas Oeschger) per E-Mail unter valise@unibas.ch oder telefonisch unter 061 207 53 33 melden.

Wir wären Ihnen sehr dankbar, wenn Sie Ihrem Kind die Erlaubnis geben würden, an unserm Forschungsprojekt teilzunehmen, um damit die Erforschung der Wertebildung in der Schule zu unterstützen.

Freundliche Grüsse

Prof. Dr. Elena Makarova & VALISE-Projektteam

----- hier abtrennen und der Klassenlehrperson abgeben -----

Einverständniserklärung zur Teilnahme am VALISE-Projekt

- Ich/Wir sind damit einverstanden, dass unser Kind am Projekt teilnimmt.
 Ich/Wir sind nicht einverstanden, dass unser Kind am Projekt teilnimmt.

Vorname/Name des Kindes _____

Name der Lehrperson: _____

Schule: _____

Vorname/Name der Erziehungsberechtigten: _____

Unterschrift der Erziehungsberechtigten: _____

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10.7 Sticker (Giveaways T1-T4)

